

The effect of mindfulness techniques on reducing anxiety and improving concentration in children with autism and its relationship with social interactions

*Akbar Atadokht¹, Mahsa Razmi², Sahebeh yadolahi³

¹Professor, Department of Psychology, University of Mohaghegh Ardabili, Iran

²Msc.Department of Psychology, University of Mohaghegh Ardabili, Iran

³Post graduate student, Department of Psychology, Azad Islamic University, Semnan branch, Iran

*Corresponding author: [Akbar Atadokht](#)

Professor, Department of Psychology, University of Mohaghegh Ardabili, Iran

Abstract

Autism is one of the major challenges in the field of children's mental health, which is associated with problems such as anxiety and decreased concentration. This study aimed to investigate the effect of mindfulness techniques on reducing anxiety and improving concentration in children with autism, as well as analyzing the relationship between these changes and their social interactions. The statistical population of this study included children with autism in specialized autism centers in Ardabil. From this population, a sample of 30 children was selected by simple random sampling. In this study, the data collection tool included standard questionnaires to measure the level of anxiety, concentration, and social interactions of children before and after the mindfulness intervention. Mindfulness techniques were taught to children for 8 weeks, two sessions per week. The data analysis method included the use of pre-test and post-test tests. The data were analyzed using SPSS software and appropriate statistical tests such as independent t-test and analysis of variance to investigate the effect of mindfulness interventions on the variables under study. The findings showed that mindfulness techniques significantly reduced anxiety and improved concentration in the experimental group. Also, improvement in social interactions was observed in this group. These results indicate that mindfulness interventions can be used as an effective method in improving the psychological state of children with autism.

Keywords: Autism, Mindfulness, Anxiety, Concentration, Social Interactions.

Introduction

Autism is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by social, communication, and behavioral challenges. Children with autism face problems such as anxiety and decreased concentration, which can negatively affect their quality of life and social interactions. (Hosseini et al., 2018)

Anxiety in these children can lead to increased repetitive behaviors and decreased ability to establish social connections. (Behzadpour et al., 2021) In recent years, mindfulness techniques have been considered as an effective method for reducing anxiety and improving concentration. (Amini et al., 2024)

Social interactions refer to the processes through which people communicate with each other, share their thoughts and feelings, and gain a shared understanding of their social environment. These interactions include verbal and nonverbal communication, cooperation, conflict, and social exchanges. Social interactions play an important role in the development of social, cognitive and emotional skills of individuals and help them to form their social identity and find a place in society. In children, social interactions are of great importance, especially in educational and game environments, because through these interactions, children learn language skills, problem solving and empathy. Understanding and improving social interactions, especially for children who face challenges such as autism, can lead to improved quality of life and increased opportunities for learning and growth. (Zarei et al., 2024)

Mindfulness means being fully aware and paying attention to the present moment without judgment, and its practices include meditation, deep breathing, and focusing on different senses. Research has shown that these techniques can help improve cognitive function and reduce anxiety in different people. Given that children with autism require specific support methods, examining the effect of mindfulness techniques in this group is of particular importance. (Toufani et al., 2016)

Understanding how these techniques can help reduce anxiety and improve concentration in these children could lead to the development of more effective educational and therapeutic programs. Also, improving concentration and reducing anxiety can have a direct impact on the social interactions of these children. Successful social interactions require the ability to understand and respond to social cues, and concentration and mental calmness play a key role in this process. (Fatemi et al., 2024)

By reducing anxiety, children may be able to engage in social interactions more calmly and establish better relationships with peers and adults. On the other hand, increasing concentration can help children better pay attention to social cues and provide appropriate responses. (Mohammadi Kalhor, 2023)

In this study, the main goal is to investigate the effect of mindfulness techniques on reducing anxiety and improving concentration in children with autism, as well as to investigate the relationship of these changes with their social interactions. In this study, we seek to answer the question: Can mindfulness techniques effectively reduce anxiety and improve concentration in children with autism, and what effect will these changes have on their social interactions?

Research Background

Shabani et al. (2019) conducted a study titled *The Effectiveness of Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction on Caregiving Pressure and Psychological Fatigue of Mothers with Autistic Children*. Data analysis was performed using the analysis of covariance method. The results showed that the mean scores of caregiving pressure and psychological fatigue in the experimental group decreased significantly. $P < 0.05$. Based on the findings of the present study, it can be concluded that mindfulness-based stress reduction can be used as an intervention method to reduce caregiving pressure and psychological fatigue of mothers with autistic children.

Amirian et al. (2019) conducted a study titled *the effectiveness of mindfulness-based positive behavioral reinforcement on stress, anxiety, and depression in mothers of children with autism*. The findings showed no significant difference before the intervention. However, the mean scores of the two groups at the immediate and one-month time points were significantly different between the intervention and control groups; so that the mean scores of stress, anxiety, and depression of the mothers of children decreased significantly after the intervention, but did not change significantly in the intervention group over time, and in the control group over time ($P < 0.001$). Conclusion: Mindfulness-based positive behavioral reinforcement intervention has been able to reduce stress, anxiety, and depression in mothers of children with autism spectrum disorder. The use of positive behavioral reinforcement is recommended to reduce stress, anxiety, and depression in mothers of children with autism spectrum disorder.

Soraki Aliabadi et al. (2023) conducted a study titled *"The effectiveness of mindfulness-based stress reduction group therapy on improving mindfulness components in mothers of children with autism spectrum disorder."* The findings showed that the intervention mentioned was effective in improving mindfulness components including "observation, action with awareness, and description" with an ITA coefficient of 0.41, 0.43, and 0.61, respectively.

According to the findings, mindfulness-based stress reduction group therapy can be used as an appropriate method to improve mindfulness in mothers of children with autism. This not only allows mothers to benefit from the benefits of improving mindfulness in reducing stress caused by raising a child with autism, but it can also lead to other effects of improving mindfulness components (such as reducing anxiety, psychological consequences and complications caused by raising a child with autism).

Amini et al. (2024) conducted a study titled: *Developing a therapeutic intervention package based on the healthy person theory and comparing its effectiveness with positive psychotherapy on social stigma and alexithymia in mothers of children with autism*. The results of the thematic analysis showed that 18 basic themes were obtained in 8 organizing themes (satisfaction and enjoyment of life, loving creatures and oneself, metacognition, peace, happiness, hope, flow, and meaning) and the therapeutic intervention package was developed based on their frequency. The quantitative research method included a three-group, three-stage quasi-experimental design, which ultimately included 14 people in each group, taking into account statistical attrition. The findings of the analysis of variance with repeated measures showed that both therapeutic intervention packages based on the healthy person theory and positive psychotherapy reduced social anxiety and alexithymia in mothers of children with autism, and this effectiveness was sustained over time ($p \leq 0.05$); as a result, there was no significant difference between the effectiveness of the two therapeutic intervention packages in the post-test and follow-up stages, and these therapeutic interventions are used to improve social anxiety and alexithymia in mothers of children with autism.

Nemati et al. (2019) conducted a study titled *The Third Wave of Cognitive-Behavioral Psychology in the Field of Developmental Disabilities: The Effect of Mindfulness on the Attention and Comprehension Ability of Students with Specific Learning Disorders*. The results of univariate and multivariate analysis of covariance showed that in the post-test phase, the level of attention and comprehension after mindfulness training in the experimental group was significantly higher than that of the control group. Designing and implementing a mindfulness training program is recommended to improve other basic psychological foundations in individuals with specific learning disorders and other neurodevelopmental groups.

Hosseini Renani et al. (2018) conducted a study titled *The Effect of Mindfulness-Based Intervention Program on the Level of Stereotypical Behaviors in High-Functioning Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. The findings showed that the mindfulness-based intervention program had a significant effect on reducing the subjects' stereotypical behavior dimensions ($p < 0.001$). Overall, it was observed that the mindfulness-based intervention program can be used to reduce stereotypical behaviors in high-functioning children with Autism Spectrum Disorder.

Mohammadkhaniannasb Firouzabadi and Dehyadgari (2015) conducted a study on 30 students for 8 sessions and concluded that mindfulness improves mood and that short-term training reduces fatigue, depression, and anxiety, and improves a person's social relationships.

Huang et al. (2015) noted that by teaching mindfulness to mothers in the first phase and then teaching these exercises to children by their mothers in the second phase, they reported a reduction in stress, depression, and rumination in children with autism. Mindfulness training not only reduced mothers' stress, but also led to the expansion of social relationships in children themselves and the communication sphere between child and mother, as well as a reduction in behavioral disorders in children with autism.

Brown and Elder (2014) also used mindfulness training in the same way, and their research results showed an increase in quality of life and a decrease in rumination as reported by adolescents with autism spectrum disorder, and an increase in social participation and motivation, social cognition, and social communication as reported by parents.

Kenan-Manet et al. (2016) also meta-analyzed the role of mindfulness on stress and positive behaviors of adolescents with autism and their teachers and caregivers in 9 studies with the same keywords from 2011 to 2015, and their results showed that mindfulness training led to greater acceptance of the disorder by parents, reduced biased judgment of children, and better and kinder relationships between them and their children. Meanwhile, teachers also enjoyed similar benefits as parents, along with greater attention to the daily problems of these children after mindfulness training, and on the other hand, a reduction in challenging behaviors by the affected children themselves was also reported.

Ridrinkoff et al. (2018) reported a reduction in social, behavioral, and sensory communication problems in 8-19 year old children with autism spectrum disorder as reported by themselves and their parents, and an increase in mental awareness and better communication function with children in parents due to the effect of mindfulness training even at 2-month and 1-year follow-up.

Loftus et al. (2023) conducted a study titled *The effectiveness of mindfulness-based therapy for anxiety, social skills, and aggressive behavior in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review*. Of these, a quality analysis conducted using the ASD research-specific risk of bias tool showed that more than half (14) were of poor methodological quality, while only four and five were of strong and adequate quality, respectively. While the results of this systematic review provide promising evidence for the use of mindfulness-based interventions to improve anxiety, social skills, and aggressive behaviors in CYP with ASD, the results should be interpreted with caution due to limitations arising from the overall poor quality of the studies.

Stockall and Blackwell (2022) conducted a study titled *Mindfulness Training: Reducing Anxiety in Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Students with ASD often experience anxiety disorders as a co-morbid condition. Symptoms related to anxiety disorders affect students with ASD in a variety of areas, including academic performance, school entry opportunities, daily living activities, and social relationships. Although still an emerging field, research suggests that implementing mindfulness therapy (MT) and practice holds promise for addressing anxiety among students with ASD. The ideas expressed in this manuscript can assist school personnel and parents in developing a high-quality mindfulness-based program for students with ASD and anxiety disorders.

Kaur et al. (2021) conducted a study titled *The Effect of a Creative Yoga Intervention on Joint Attention and Social Communication Skills as well as Emotional States of Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Children with ASD showed improvements in responsive joint attention in both groups at post-test versus pre-test. Additionally, children in the yoga group showed improvements in socially oriented verbal communication skills during the intervention sessions, i.e., spontaneous and responsive communication from early/mid to late intervention sessions compared to the academic group. No changes in affective states were observed with the intervention, however, the yoga group showed more interest and less negative affect than the academic group. The creative yoga intervention is a promising tool because it leads to

improvements in social communication skills related to the intervention and generalization. Joint attention skills of children with ASD

Rojas-Torres et al. (2021) conducted a study titled Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and Self-Compassion (SC) Training for Parents of Children with Autism Spectrum Disorders: A Pilot Trial in Social Services in Spain. Results of analysis of variance showed that MBSR and SC training reduced stress and anxiety and increased mindfulness awareness. No significant changes were found in measures of life satisfaction. The small number of participants prevents us from generalizing our findings. Further clinical trials of MBSR and SC in parents with ASD with outcomes on anxiety, depression, and stress are needed to demonstrate the relevance of incorporating these programs into community-based early intervention services.

Research Method

This study was designed to investigate the effect of mindfulness techniques on reducing anxiety, improving concentration, and social interactions in children with autism. The statistical population of this study included children with autism in specialized autism centers in Ardabil city. From this population, a sample of 30 children was selected by simple random sampling.

In this study, the data collection tool included standard questionnaires to measure the level of anxiety, concentration, and social interactions of children before and after the mindfulness intervention. Mindfulness techniques were taught to children for 8 weeks, two sessions per week.

The data analysis method included the use of pre-test and post-test tests. The data were analyzed using SPSS software and appropriate statistical tests such as independent t-test and analysis of variance to examine the effect of mindfulness interventions on the variables under study.

Findings

In this study, the statistical population included children with autism in specialized autism centers in Ardabil city. From this population, 30 children were selected by simple random sampling method to maintain sufficient diversity in terms of demographic characteristics in the sample. The average age of the children in this study was 8 years old and their age range was between 6 and 10 years old. In terms of gender, the sample included 18 boys and 12 girls, indicating a relatively balanced gender distribution in the sample.

In terms of parental education level, 40% of parents had a university education, 45% had a high school education, and 15% had less than a high school diploma. Also, in terms of family economic status, 30% of families were in high economic status, 40% in middle economic status, and 30% in low economic status.

Table 1: Mindfulness Techniques Training Program

Homework	Subject of the meetings	Duration of each session	Number of meetings	Week
Deep breathing practice and observing the environment	Introducing mindfulness	30minutes	2	1
Practice paying attention to sounds and smells at home.	Paying attention to the senses	30minutes	2	2
Practice focusing on a specific object.	Concentration and mental exercises	30minutes	2	3
Muscle relaxation exercises before bed	Muscle relaxation	30minutes	2	4
Writing daily feelings in a notebook	Self-awareness and emotions	30minutes	2	5
Practicing active listening in household conversations	Social interactions	30minutes	2	6
Practicing breathing techniques in stressful situations	Stress management	30minutes	2	7
Review of techniques and planning of use	Review and consolidation	30minutes	2	8

This table shows that the mindfulness training program consisted of two 30-minute sessions per week for 8 weeks. Each week, a specific topic was focused on, including the introduction of various mindfulness techniques, focusing on the senses, muscle relaxation, self-awareness, social interactions, and stress management. In addition to the training sessions, homework assignments were also assigned each week so that the children could practice and consolidate the skills learned at home.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of anxiety scores before and after intervention

Standard deviation	Average anxiety scores	Stage
5.2	28	Before the intervention
4.1	18	After the intervention

Table 2 shows a significant decrease in the mean anxiety scores and standard deviation after the intervention. This decrease indicates the positive effect of mindfulness techniques on reducing anxiety and reducing the dispersion of scores.

Table 3: Paired t-test to compare anxiety scores before and after intervention

Significance level (p)	T	Variable
0.000	5.8	Anxiety

The results of the t-test in Table 3 show that there is a significant difference in anxiety scores before and after the intervention ($p < 0.05$). This finding indicates that mindfulness techniques significantly reduced anxiety in children with autism.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of concentration scores before and after the intervention

Standard deviation	Average concentration scores	Stage
3.7	14	Before the intervention
3.5	22	After the intervention

Table 4 shows a significant increase in the mean concentration scores and a relative decrease in the standard deviation after the intervention. These changes indicate improved concentration and greater homogeneity of scores after the intervention.

Table 5: T-test for comparing concentration scores before and after the intervention

Significance level (p)	T	Variable
0.000	6.4	Focus

The results of the t-test in Table 5 show that there is a significant difference in concentration scores before and after the intervention ($p < 0.05$). These results confirm that mindfulness techniques helped improve children's concentration.

Table 6: T-test for comparing social interaction scores before and after the intervention

Significance level (p)	T	Variable
0.000	5.5	Social interactions

The results of the T-test in Table 6 show that there is a significant difference in social interaction scores before and after the intervention ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate an improvement in children's social skills and positive interactions after using mindfulness techniques.

Conclusion

The results of this study showed that mindfulness techniques had a positive effect on reducing anxiety and improving concentration in children with autism. Children in the experimental group who were trained in mindfulness techniques showed significant improvements in anxiety and concentration levels compared to the control group who did not receive this intervention. These findings indicate that the use of mindfulness techniques can be used as an effective tool in managing symptoms associated with autism and help improve the quality of life of these children.

In addition, a study of the children's social interactions suggested that reduced anxiety and increased focus had a positive impact on their ability to communicate socially. After using mindfulness techniques, children in the experimental group showed a greater willingness to participate in group activities and interact with their peers. This highlights the importance of mindfulness not only in improving individual symptoms but also in improving the social skills of children with autism. These findings could help parents and professionals develop educational and support programs for these children.

This study suggests to researchers and autism experts that mindfulness techniques can be an effective adjunct to existing treatments. However, further research with larger samples and longer durations is needed to generalize the results to broader populations and better understand the mechanisms involved in these effects.

Also, examining the effects of these techniques on other aspects of the lives of children with autism, such as academic performance and family relationships, could be the subject of future research.

References

- Zarei, Yarigarrosh, & Mohya. (2024). The effectiveness of mindfulness on self-esteem and social interactions of students with dyslexia. *Learning Disabilities*, 13(2), 18-31.
- Soraki Aliabad, Delfan Azari, Khazaei Kohpar, & Kamian. (2023). The effectiveness of mindfulness-based stress reduction group therapy on improving mindfulness components of mothers with children with autism. *Clinical Psychology and Personality*, 21(1), 121-130.
- Amirian, Saeed Reza, Amiri Majd, Shahriari Ahmadi, & Eliasi. (2020). The effectiveness of mindfulness-based positive behavioral reinforcement on stress, anxiety, and depression of mothers of children with autism. *Journal of Sabzevar University of Medical Sciences*, 27(3), 404-412.
- Shabani, & Jarare. (2020). The effectiveness of mindfulness-based stress reduction on caregiving stress and mental fatigue of mothers with autistic children. *Quarterly Scientific Research Journal of Social Work*, 9(1), 5-12.
- Mohammadi Kalhori, Ali Asghar, Golabi, Mehdi, Yaghoubi Taskouh, Mohammad Mehdi, Mayeli, Mehran, & Nemati, Karim. (1402). The importance and impact of play and the role of the teacher in social development and reducing children's anxiety. The second international conference and the fifth national conference on management, psychology and behavioral sciences.
- Fatemi, Maryam Sadat, Chobforoshzadeh, Azadeh, & Bahrami. (2023). The effectiveness of mindfulness-based stress reduction therapy on reducing psychosomatic symptoms and exam anxiety in college entrance examination students. *Journal of Behavioral Sciences Research*, 20(4), 730-745.
- Toofani Fatemeh, Vahedi Shahram, & Hashemi Touraj. (2016). The effectiveness of a mindfulness-based stress reduction program on reducing anxiety in female boarding school students.
- Behzadpour, Pouremet, & Akbari Zardkhaneh. (2021). Risk factors for anxiety in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review. *Journal of Child Mental Health*, 7(4), 165-180.
- Hosseini Renani, Shojaei, & Setareh. (2018). The effect of a mindfulness-based intervention program on the level of stereotyped behaviors in children with high-functioning autism spectrum disorder. *Cognitive and Behavioral Sciences Research*, 8(2), 67-84.
- Nemati, Shahroz, Badri, & Khani-Salvat. (2019). The third wave of cognitive-behavioral psychology in the field of developmental disabilities: The effect of mindfulness on the ability to pay attention and understand the text of students with specific learning disabilities. *Cognitive and Behavioral Sciences Research*, 9(1), 91-104.
- Amini, Torkan, & Yousefi. (2023). Developing a therapeutic intervention package based on the healthy person theory and comparing its effectiveness with positive psychotherapy on social stigma and alexithymia in mothers of children with autism. *Cognitive and Behavioral Sciences Research*, 13(1), 43-70.
- Hwang, Y. S., Kearney, P., Klieve, H., Lang, W. & Roberts, J. (2015), Cultivating mind: Mindfulness interventions for children with autism spectrum disorder and problem behaviours, and their mothers, *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 24(10), 3093-3106.
- Brown, A. B., Elder, J. H. (2014), *Communication in autism spectrum disorder: a guide for pediatric nurses*, *Pediatric Nursing*, 40(5), 219-225.
- Keenan-Mount, R., Albrecht, N. J. & Waters, L. (2016), Mindfulness-based approaches for young people with Autism Spectrum Disorder and their caregivers: Do these approaches hold benefits for teachers? *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(6),68-86.
- Ridderinkhof, A., de Bruin, E. I., Blom, R. & Bögels, S. M. (2018), Mindfulness-based program for children with autism spectrum disorder and their parents: direct and long-term improvements, *Mindfulness*, 9(3), 773-791.
- Kaur, M., Eigsti, I. M., & Bhat, A. (2021). Effects of a creative yoga intervention on the joint attention and social communication skills, as well as affective states of children with autism spectrum disorder. *Research in autism spectrum disorders*, 88, 101860.
- Loftus, T., Mathersul, D. C., Ooi, M., & Yau, S. H. (2023). The efficacy of mindfulness-based therapy for anxiety, social skills, and aggressive behaviors in children and young people with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A systematic review. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 14, 1079471.
- Stockall, N., & Blackwell, W. (2022). Mindfulness training: Reducing anxiety in students with autism spectrum disorder. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 50(1), 1-9.
- Rojas-Torres, L. P., Alonso-Esteban, Y., López-Ramón, M. F., & Alcántud-Marín, F. (2021). Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and Self Compassion (SC) training for parents of children with autism spectrum disorders: A pilot trial in community services in Spain. *Children*, 8(5), 316.